

Jordan Dedekind Chain Condition on Pre-A* Posets with Graphical Aspects

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ABSTRACT

Jordan Dedekind chain condition on pre-A* posets is studied. We discuss isomorphism of pre-A* posets, ascending chain condition and descending chain condition on pre-A* posets. We also prove that a pre-A* poset possessing a least element of locally finite length which satisfies Jordan Dedekind chain condition has a dimension function.

KEYWORDS: Pre-A* algebra, poset, chain, isomorphism, ascending chain condition, descending chain condition, Jordan Dedekind chain condition.

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1 INTRODUCTION

An equational 3-valued generalization of a boolean algebra and C-algebra have been introduced by Fernando [1]. The aforesaid generalization based on logic functions “and”, “or” and “not”. The algebra of disjoint alternatives (Ada) $(A, \wedge, \vee, (-)^\sim, (-)^\neg, 0, 1, 2)$ has been studied by Manes [2], building a foundation on C-algebras. An A*-algebra $(A, \wedge, \vee, (-)^\sim, (-)^\neg, 0, 1, 2)$ and its equivalence with algebra of disjoint alternatives as well as the association of C-algebras and 3-ring has been done by Rao [3]. Moreover, A*-clones, If-Then-Else structure over A*-algebra, pre-A* algebra $(A, \wedge, \vee, (-)^\sim)$ and ideal of A*-algebra have been investigated [3, 4]. Kalyani [5, 6] have characterized a partial order relation on pre-A* algebra, thereby studying representation of a pre-A* algebra by a partial order. In this work, we prove that if a Pre-A* poset has least element of locally finite length which satisfies the Jordan Dedekind chain condition, then the pre-A* poset has a dimension function. The theorem is based on ascending and descending chain conditions.

2 Preliminaries

In this part of the paper, we define the important terms that we have used throughout.

Definition 1 (Pre-A* algebra). [4, Definition 1] A Pre-A* algebra is an algebra $(A, \wedge, \vee, (-)^\sim)$ where A has a 1; \wedge and \vee are binary operations and $(-)^\sim$ is a unary operation such that the following conditions are satisfied:

- (i). $x^{\sim\sim} = x$ for all $x \in A$,
- (ii). $x \wedge x = x$, for all $x \in A$,

(iii). $x \wedge y = y \wedge x$, for all $x, y \in A$,

(iv). $(x \wedge y)^\sim = x^\sim \vee y^\sim$ for all $x, y \in A$,

(v). $x \wedge (y \wedge z) = (x \wedge y) \wedge z$ for all $x, y, z \in A$, (vi). $x \wedge (y \vee z) = (x \wedge y) \vee (x \wedge z)$ for all $x, y, z \in A$,

(vii). $x \wedge y = x \wedge (x^\sim \vee y)$ for all $x, y \in A$.

Example 1. (i). Let $(\mathbf{3} = \{0, 1, 2\}, \wedge, \vee, (-)^\sim)$ be a pre-A* algebra. The operations are defined using the laws: $2^\sim = 2$, $1 \wedge x = x$ for all $x \in \mathbf{3}$, $0 \vee x = x$ for all $x \in \mathbf{3}$ and $2 \wedge x = 2 \vee x = 2$ for all $x \in \mathbf{3}$. Hence we obtain Table 1.

Table 1: An illustration of the properties in Example 1(i).

\wedge	0	1	2	\vee	0	1	2	x	x^\sim
0	0	0	2	0	0	1	2	0	1
1	0	1	2	1	1	1	2	1	0
2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2

(a) \wedge . (b) \vee . (c) $(-)^\sim$.

(ii). Let $(\mathbf{2} = \{0, 1\}, \wedge, \vee, (-)^\sim)$ be a pre-A* algebra. The operations are defined using the laws: $1 \wedge x = x$ for all $x \in \mathbf{2}$, $0 \vee x = x$ for all $x \in \mathbf{2}$. Hence we obtain Table 2.

Table 2: An illustration of the properties in Example 1(ii).

\wedge	0	1	\vee	0	1	x	x^\sim
0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1
1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0

(a) \wedge . (b) \vee . (c) $(-)^\sim$.

Definition 2. [4, Partial order] A relation R on a set A is partial order if:

- (i). For all $a \in A, aRa$ (reflexivity)
- (ii). For all $a, b \in A, aRb$ and bRa , then $a = b$ (anti-symmetry)
- (iii). For all $a, b, c \in A, aRb$ and bRc , then aRc (transitivity).

The pair (A, R) is a partially ordered set (poset).

Example 2. Posets

- (i). Let $A = \{0, 1, 2\}$. Then power set of A given by $2^A = \{\emptyset, \{0\}, \{1\}, \{2\}, \{0, 1\}, \{0, 2\}, \{1, 2\}, A\}$ is a poset under set inclusion. For any $A_0, A_1 \subseteq A$, we define $A_0 \leq A_1$ whenever $A_0 \subseteq A_1$. The pair $(2^A, \subseteq)$ is a poset.
- (ii). Let P be the set of all real-valued functions on $A = \{0, 1\}$. That is, $P = \{f \mid f : A \rightarrow \mathbb{R}\}$. For any $f_0, f_1 \in P$ let $f_0 \leq f_1$ as long as for any $t \in A$, then $f_0(t) \leq f_1(t)$. The pair (P, \leq) is a poset.

Remark 1. Let (A, R) be a poset. Then $a_0, a_1 \in A$ are comparable if either a_0Ra_1 or a_1Ra_0 . Else a_0 and a_1 are incomparable. A poset in which any two members can be compared is a chain. For instance:

- (i). Let $A \neq \emptyset$ be a set with a power set 2^A . Then $(2^A, \subseteq)$ is a poset as described in Example 2 (i). In particular, if $A = \{0, 1\}$, then $2^A = \{\emptyset, \{0\}, \{1\}, A\}$. The elements $\{0\}$ and $\{1\}$ in 2^A are not comparable by set inclusion. So, $(2^A, \subseteq)$ is merely a poset but not a chain.
- (ii). The Pre-A* algebra $(\mathbf{3} = \{0, 1, 2\}, \wedge, \vee, (-)\sim)$ with R defined as $a_0 \leq a_1$ whenever $a_0 \wedge a_1 = a_1 \wedge a_0 = a_0$ for any $a_0, a_1 \in \mathbf{3}$ is a chain.

Let $(\emptyset \neq A_0, \leq)$ be any subset of a poset (A, \leq) . Observe that \leq induces a partial ordering on A_0 , and hence, $(\emptyset \neq A_0, \leq)$ is a poset (a subposet). In the same spirit, any subset of a chain is also a chain (a subchain).

Definition 3. Let (A_1, \leq_1) and (A_2, \leq_2) be posets. A mapping $\phi : A_1 \rightarrow A_2$ is an order-preserving homomorphism or isotone, if $a_1 \leq_1 a'_1$ implies that $\phi(a_1) \leq_2 \phi(a'_1)$ for all $a_1, a'_1 \in A_1$. If ϕ is a bijection and $a_1 \leq_1 a'_1$ if and only if $\phi(a_1) \leq_2 \phi(a'_1)$ for all $a_1, a'_1 \in A_1$ (that is, ϕ and ϕ^{-1} are order-preserving homomorphisms), then ϕ is an isomorphism (order-preserving isomorphism). An isomorphism from A_1 to itself is called an automorphism.

Definition 4. Let (A, \leq) be a poset. An element $a \in A$ is said to be the least (greatest) element of A if $a \leq x$ ($x \leq a$) for all $x \in A$. If A is a Pre-A* algebra, then $c \in A$ is a central element if $c \vee c^\sim = 1$. In the Pre-A* algebra $(\mathbf{3} = \{0, 1, 2\}, \wedge, \vee, (-)\sim)$, 0 and 1 are central elements whereas 2 is a non-central element. A Pre-A* algebra A which satisfies the conditions of a poset is a pre-A* poset. We illustrate as follows:

- (i). If A is a pre-A* algebra with 1, 0, and 2, then $x \leq 1$ ($x \wedge 1 = 1 \wedge x = x$) for all $x \in A$, and $2 \leq x$ ($x \wedge 2 = 2 \wedge x = 2$). This shows that 1 is the greatest element and 2 is the least element of the poset, since $2 \leq x \leq 1$. The Hasse diagram for the poset (A, \leq) is given in Figure 1 below.

Fig. 1: Hasse diagram of the poset (A, \leq) .

The chromatic number of the graph in Figure 1 is 2. It is thus a bipartite graph. This graph has two nodes of odd degree, making it have an Euler path but no Euler circuit.

- (ii). Let $A \times A = \{a_1 = (1, 1), a_2 = (1, 0), a_3 = (1, 2), a_4 = (0, 1), a_5 = (0, 0), a_6 = (0, 2), a_7 = (2, 1), a_8 = (2, 0), a_9 = (2, 2)\}$ be a pre-A* algebra under pointwise operation. Then $A \times A$ has four central elements and the rest noncentral. Among them, $a_9 = (2, 2)$ satisfies the property that $a_9 = a_9^\sim$. The Hasse diagram of the poset $(A \times A, \leq)$ is given in Figure 2 below, where a_7 is the top element.

Fig. 2: Hasse Diagram for $A \times A$.

The chromatic number of the graph in Figure 2 is 2, making it a bipartite graph. It is a planar graph since there are no edge crossings, and the planar representation is provided in Figure 3.

Fig. 3: Planar representation of the graph in Figure 2.

It's a planar graph with 5 regions. Here we can observe that $x \leq a_1$, $x \wedge a_1 = a_1 \wedge x = x$, and $a_9 \leq x$ ($x \wedge a_9 = a_9 \wedge x = a_9$) for all $x \in A \times A$. This means that a_1 is the greatest element and a_9 is the least element of $A \times A$.

(iii). We have that $2 \times 3 = \{a_1 = (1,1), a_2 = (1,0), a_3 = (1,0), a_4 = (0,1), a_5 = (0,2), a_6 = (1,2)\}$ is a Pre-A* algebra under pointwise operation, having four central elements, two non-central elements, and no element satisfying the property that $a \sim = a$. The Hasse diagram for $(2 \times 3, \leq)$ is given below in Figure 4. Observe that $x \leq a_1$, that is, $x \wedge a_1 = a_1 \wedge x = x$, and $a_5 \leq x$ ($x \wedge a_5 = a_5 \wedge x = a_5$) for all $x \in 2 \times 3$. This shows that a_1 is the greatest element and a_5 is the least element of 2×3 . The graph has a chromatic number of 3, hence it is not a bipartite. It's a planar graph with 4 regions as shown in Figure 5.

Fig. 4: The Hasse diagram for 2×3 .

Fig. 5: The Planar representation of graph in Figure 4.

Definition 5. Let $A \neq \emptyset$ be a set. Then $a \in A$ is a minimal element if A has no a^0 such that $a^0 < a$ (or $a^0 \leq a$ implies $a^0 = a$). Similarly, $a \in A$ is a maximal element if there exists no $a^0 \in A$ has such that $a < a^0$ (or $a \leq a^0$ implies $a = a^0$).

- (i). Consider the pre-A* posets represented in the Figures 1 and 2. In Figure 1, one can observe that 2 is the minimal element and 1 is the maximal element. In Figure 2, one can observe that a_9 is the minimal element and a_1 is the maximal element.
- (ii). Consider the poset $P = \{1,2,3,4,5,6\}$ with the definition $x \leq y$ if and only if x divides y for all $x, y \in P$. See the Hasse diagram in Figure 6 below. In P , 1 is a minimal element and 4, 5, and 6 are maximal elements because 4, 5, and 6 have no x in P to divide (that is, there is no x in P such that $4 < x$, $5 < x$, and $6 < x$), whereas 1, 2, and 3 have some x to divide (that is $1 \leq x$ for all x in P , $2 \leq 4$, $2 \leq 6$, and $3 \leq 6$). This graph has a chromatic number of 3 and thus is not bipartite.

Fig. 6: Hasse Diagram representing the relations in P Definition 5 (ii)

Definition 6. Let A be a Pre-A* algebra. The length of a chain of the form $a_0 < a_1 < \dots < a_{r-1}$ consisting of r elements is a non-negative integer $r - 1$. This corresponds to a path of length $r - 1$, connecting the vertices a_0 and a_{r-1} . The length $l(A)$ of a poset (A, \leq) is the least upper bound (lub) of the lengths of all subchains of A , that is $l(A) = \text{lub}\{l(C) \mid C \text{ is a chain in } A\}$.

- (i). Let us consider the poset represented by the Figure 1. In this poset, $2 \leq 0 \leq 1$ is the chain of length 2. Then, the length of the poset A is given by $l(A) = \text{lub}\{l(C) \mid C \text{ is a chain in } A\} = \text{lub}\{2\} = 2$.
- (ii). Consider the poset $(A \times A, \leq)$ represented in Figure 2. The chains are: $a_9 \leq a_8 \leq a_7 \leq a_4 \leq a_1$; $a_9 \leq a_6 \leq a_3 \leq a_2 \leq a_1$; $a_9 \leq a_8 \leq a_5 \leq a_2 \leq a_1$; $a_9 \leq a_6 \leq a_5 \leq a_4 \leq a_1$. These are analogous to paths of length 4 connecting vertices a_9 and a_1 .
- (iii). In the Pre-A* poset 2×3 , from Hasse diagram in Figure 4, the chains connecting a_5 and a_1 are given by: $a_5 \leq a_4 \leq a_1$; $a_5 \leq a_2 \leq a_4 \leq a_1$; $a_5 \leq a_6 \leq a_3 \leq a_1$; and $a_5 \leq a_2 \leq a_3 \leq a_1$.

If C is a subchain in A , then $l(C) \leq l(A)$. The poset (A, \leq) is of finite length if $l(A)$ is finite. Observe that all finite posets are of finite lengths. A poset A is of locally finite length if every one of its intervals is of finite length.

Remark 2. The interval in a poset is the set of all the elements in between the least and greatest elements, including them. For example, $a_9 \leq a_8 \leq a_7 \leq a_4 \leq a_1$ is a chain connecting a_9 and a_1 . So, the elements of this chain are the elements of the interval $[a_9, a_1]$ and hence the length of the interval is computed in a similar way as defined above. In the poset $(A \times A, \leq)$ represented in Figure 2, we can observe that all intervals connecting a_9 and a_1 are of finite length. Therefore, the poset $(A \times A, \leq)$ is of locally finite length. Any $x \in A$ is an upper (lower) bound of $R \subset (A, \leq)$ if $a \leq x$ ($x \leq a$) for all a in R . If R has at least one upper (lower) bound, then R is said to be bounded above (below). A subset R of a poset (A, \leq) , which is both bounded and below, is said to be a bounded subset of (A, \leq) . If (A, \leq) is a poset, then for a in A , $(a) = \{x \in A \mid x \leq a\}$ is the set of all lower bounds of a in (A, \leq) . Similarly, $[a] = \{x \in A \mid a \leq x\}$ is the set of all upper bounds of a in (A, \leq) . Consider the following illustration on posets and boundedness.

- (i). In the poset $(A \times A = \{a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4, a_5, a_6, a_7, a_8, a_9\}, \leq)$ shown in Figure 2, consider the subset $R = \{a_5, a_6, a_8, a_3\}$. Here $a_9 \leq a_8$, $a_9 \leq a_6$, $a_9 \leq a_5$, $a_9 \leq a_3$. So a_9 is a lower bound of R .
- (ii). Consider the subset $S = \{a_4, a_2\}$ in the poset $(A \times A, \leq)$ in Figure 2. Since $a_5 \leq a_4$ and $a_5 \leq a_2$ and $a_6 \leq a_4$ and $a_6 \leq a_2$, the set $\{a_5, a_6\}$ is a lower bound of $S = \{a_4, a_2\}$.
- (iii). As for the set $\{a_1, a_2, a_4\}$ in Figure 2, a_1 has no upper bound. In the set $\{a_8, a_9, a_6\}$, a_9 has no lower bound.

Definition 7. Let R be any subset of a poset $A = \{0, 1, 2\}$. If there exists a lower (upper) bound of R that is also an element of R , then it is called the least (greatest) element of R . Let us denote it by $\underline{2}$ ($\overline{1}$). That is, if a is the least (greatest) element

of R , then $a \leq x$ ($x \leq a$) for all x in R and a in R . The elements other than $\underline{2}$ and $\overline{1}$ are called inner elements of R . The least and greatest elements together will be called bound elements. Consider the poset $A \times A$ as shown in Figure 2 and $R = \{a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4\}$. The element a_1 is the maximal in R and $x \leq a_1$ for all x in R . So, R has an upper bound and R has a greatest element. An element x is a greatest lower bound (least upper bound) or infimum (supremum) of R if x is the greatest (least) element of all lower (upper) bounds of R . Consider the subset $R = \{a_8, a_5, a_6\}$ in the poset $A \times A$ as shown in Figure 2. Then $\text{Sup}(\{a_8, a_6\}) = a_5$. If $R = \{a_8, a_9, a_6\}$, then $\text{Inf}(\{a_8, a_6\}) = a_9$.

Definition 8. Let (A, \leq) be a poset. Then A satisfies the minimum (maximum) condition or descending chain condition (DCC) (ascending chain condition (ACC)) if for any descending (ascending) sequence $a_1 \geq a_2 \geq a_3 \geq \dots$ ($a_1 \leq a_2 \leq a_3 \leq \dots$) of elements of A , there exists a positive integer n such that $a_n = a_{n+1} = \dots$. Every finite poset satisfies ACC and DCC. One can observe ACC and DCC in the finite posets $(A \times A = \{a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4, a_5, a_6, a_7, a_8, a_9\}, \leq)$ in Figure 2 and $(A = \{0, 1, 2\}, \leq)$ shown in Figure 1.

Definition 9. Let (A, \leq) be a Pre-A* poset. For any $a, b \in A$ such that $a < b$, let C be a subchain of A having a as the least element and b as the greatest element. Then we say that C is situated between the elements a and b , or C connects a and b . Graphically, we note that the path C is situated between a and b , or C connects a and b .

Definition 10. Let A be a Pre-A* algebra. If for every pair of elements a, b such that $a \leq b$ in a Pre-A* poset (A, \leq) , it is true that all maximal chains connecting the elements a and b are of the same length, then (A, \leq) is said to satisfy the Jordan Dedekind Chain condition (JDCC), that is, all the maximal paths connecting the elements a and b are of the same length.

Definition 11. Let (A, \leq) be a pre-A* poset which is bounded below. Let $a \in A$. We define the height $h(a)$ or dimension of the element a as the length of the maximal chain that connects the least element a^0 and a . That is, $h(a) = l([a^0, a])$.

Definition 12. Let (A, \leq) be a pre-A* poset which is bounded below and of locally finite length satisfying JDCC. Then $x < y$ if and only if $x \leq y$ and $h(x) + 1 = h(y)$. (Here $x < y$ will be called "x covered by y" and it means that there is no element z between x and y such that $x \leq z \leq y$). For instance, from Figure 2:

- (i). It can be observed that $a_2 < a_1$ if and only if $a_2 \leq a_1$ and $h(a_2) + 1 = h(a_1)$. This implies, $h(a_1) = 3 + 1 = 4$.
- (ii). Further, $a_9 < a_6$ if and only if $a_9 \leq a_6$ and $h(a_9) + 1 = h(a_6)$. This implies, $h(a_6) = 0 + 1 = 1$.

Definition 13. Let (A, \leq) be a pre-A* poset (not necessarily bounded below) and let $d : A \rightarrow \mathbb{Z} \cup \{\pm\infty\}$ be an integer valued function whose co-domain includes integers and one or both of symbols $\pm\infty$. Then d is called the dimension function of A if $x < y$ if and only if $x \leq y$ and $d(x) + 1 = d(y)$ for all x, y in A .

3 MAIN RESULTS

We use this section to present main results in the manuscript.

Lemma 1. *Let A be a pre-A* algebra. Define a relation \leq on A by $x \leq y$ if and only if $y \wedge x = x \wedge y = x$. Then (A, \leq) is a poset.*

Proof. Since $x \wedge x = x$, $x \leq x$ for all $x \in A$. Therefore, \leq is reflexive. For all $x, y \in A$, whenever $x \leq y$, and $y \leq x$, then $y \wedge x = x \wedge y = x$ and $y \wedge x = x \wedge y = y$. So $x = y$ and \leq is anti-symmetric. Now let $x, y, z \in A$ such that $x \leq y$ and $y \leq z$. Then $y \wedge x = x \wedge y = x$ and $z \wedge y = y \wedge z = y$. Now, $x = x \wedge y = x \wedge y \wedge z = x \wedge z$, which means that $x \wedge z = z \wedge x = x$. Therefore, $x \leq z$. Consequently, \leq is transitive and (A, \leq) is a poset.

Proposition 1. *Let $A = \{0, 1, 2\}$ and 2^A be the power set of A . Then 2^A is a bounded set.*

Proof. For any A_0, A_1 in 2^A , define $A_0 \leq A_1$ whenever $A_0 \subseteq A_1$. Clearly, $\emptyset \subseteq A_0$ for all A_0 in 2^A . Then, $\emptyset \leq A_0$ for all $A_0 \in 2^A$. Thus, \emptyset is the lower bound of 2^A . Moreover, for any $A_0 \in 2^A$, $A_0 \subseteq A$ for all $A_0 \in 2^A$. Then $A_0 \leq A$ for all $A_0 \in 2^A$. Thus, A is the upper bound of 2^A and $\emptyset \leq A_0 \leq A$ for all $A_0 \in 2^A$. Hence, 2^A is a bounded set.

Lemma 2. *Let A be any poset. If A has a lower (upper) bound, then it has at most one lower (upper) bound.*

Proof. We prove uniqueness of the lower bound and the same idea can be adopted to suit the upper bound case. Suppose that A has two lower bounds, say a and b . Since a is a lower bound of A , then

$$a \leq b. \quad (1)$$

Since b is a lower bound of A , then

$$b \leq a. \quad (2)$$

$b \leq a$. Since \leq is antisymmetric, then by Equations (1)-(2), it follows that $a = b$. Similarly, it can be shown that A has at most one upper bound.

Corollary 1. *In a poset (A, \leq) , if A has a least (greatest) element, then it is the only minimal (maximal) element of A .*

Proof. Let A have a least element a . Then

$$a \leq x, \quad (3)$$

for all $x \in A$ and $a \in A$. We claim that a is the minimal element of A . Assume to the contrary that a is not a minimal element of A . Then, there exists x in A such that

$$x \leq a. \quad (4)$$

Since (A, \leq) is a poset, Equations (3)-(4) and anti-symmetry imply that $a = x$ is the minimal element of A . Since a is the least element of A , a is unique by Lemma 2. Therefore, a is the only minimal element of A . Similarly, we prove that if A has a greatest element, then it is the only maximal element of A .

Theorem 2. *Let A_1 and A_2 be posets and let ϕ be an order isomorphism of A_1 onto*

A_2 . If a subset R_1 of A_1 has an infimum in A_1 , then the set $R_2 = \{\phi(x) \mid x \in R_1\}$ has an infimum in A_2 . That is, $\inf_{A_2}(R_2) = \{\phi(x) \mid x \in R_1\}$ or $\inf_{A_2}(\phi(R_1)) = \phi(\inf_{A_1}(R_1))$.

Proof. Let $\inf_{A_1}(R_1) = a$. This implies that for every x in R_1 , $a \leq x$ in A_1 . Since ϕ is an order isomorphism, we have that

$$\phi(a) \leq \phi(x), \quad (5)$$

in A_2 for all x in R_1 . Hence, $\phi(a)$ is a lower bound of $\phi(R_1)$.

We prove that

$$\phi(a) = \text{glb}(\phi(R_1)). \quad (6)$$

Let $t \in A_2$ be any other lower bound of $\phi(R_1)$. Since ϕ is onto, there exists b in A_1 such that $\phi(b) = t$. Therefore, $t = \phi(b)$ is a lower bound of $\phi(R_1)$. Since x is any element of R_1 , $\phi(b) \leq \phi(x)$ for all x in R_1 , implies that $b \leq x$ (since ϕ is order preserving) for all x in R_1 . Then b is a lower bound of R_1 . Hence, $b \leq a$, since $a = \text{glb}(R_1)$. So, $\phi(b) \leq \phi(a)$. This implies, $t \leq \phi(a)$. (7)

By (5), (6), and (7), we conclude that $\phi(a)$ is a lower bound of $\phi(R_1)$, and for any lower bound t of $\phi(R_1)$, we have that $t \leq \phi(a)$. Therefore, $\phi(a) = \text{glb}_{A_2}(\phi(R_1)) = \inf_{A_2}(\phi(R_1))$. That is, $\phi(\inf_{A_1}(R_1)) = \inf_{A_2}(\phi(R_1))$.

Theorem 3. *If a poset (A, \leq) satisfies the minimum (maximum) condition, then for any x in A , there exists one element m of A such that $m \leq x$ ($x \leq m$).*

Proof. Suppose that A satisfies the minimum condition (DCC). Let $x \in A$. If x is minimal, then $x = m$. If x is not minimal, then there exists $x_1 \in A$ such that $x_1 \leq x$. If x_1 is not minimal, then there exists $x_2 \in A$ such that $x_2 \leq x_1 \leq x$. If we continue this process, then we have a descending sequence of elements of A . But by hypothesis, A satisfies the minimum condition (DCC). Therefore, the above process must be terminated at a certain stage, say x_r , and no element of A will be less than x_r . Hence, x_r is a minimal element of A . That is, $x_r \leq x$ for all x in A . Similarly, we can prove that if a poset A satisfies the maximum condition, then it has a maximal element.

Corollary 2. *Let (A, \leq) be a chain. Then every subchain of (A, \leq) satisfying the maximum (minimum) condition has a greatest (least) element.*

Proof. Suppose that a poset A satisfies the maximum condition. Then, every subset of A also satisfies the maximum condition. Since every subchain of a poset A is also a subset of A , every subchain of A satisfies the maximum condition. We know that a chain does not have more than one maximal element, and that maximal element is the greatest element of the chain. Therefore, every subchain of A satisfies the maximum condition. Every chain of the form $a_1 < a_2 < a_3 \dots$ does not contain an infinite number of elements. Therefore, after a certain stage, that is, after a finite number of steps, we obtain a maximal element, which is also the greatest element. Similarly, we can prove that every subchain of a poset satisfying the minimum condition has a least element.

Theorem 4. *Let (A, \leq) be a poset. Then (A, \leq) can satisfy both the maximum and minimum conditions if and only if every one of its subchains is of finite length.*

Proof. Suppose A is a poset that satisfies both the maximum and minimum conditions. Let C be a subchain of A . We prove that C is of finite length. Since A satisfies the minimum condition, then by Corollary 2, C has a minimal element, say x_1 , and hence x_1 is a least element of C . Define $C_1 = C \setminus \{x_1\}$. Then C_1 is again a subchain of A . Let x_2 be the least element

of C_1 . Therefore, we have $x_1 < x_2$. If we continue this process, we obtain an ascending sequence $x_1 < x_2 < x_3 \dots$ of elements of C and hence elements of A . But A satisfies the maximum condition. Therefore, the above sequence must be finite. Therefore, C is finite. That is, every subchain of A is of finite length. Conversely, suppose that every subchain of a poset A is of finite length. We prove that A satisfies both the maximum and minimum conditions. Assume to the contrary that A does not satisfy the minimum condition. Then there exists x_0 in A such that starting from x_0 , we can obtain an infinite number of elements $x_1 > x_2 > x_3 \dots$. Put $C = \{x_r\}_{r=0}^\infty$. Then clearly C is a subchain of A that is infinite, which contradicts the fact that every subchain of a poset is finite. Therefore, A satisfies the minimum condition. Similarly, we can prove that A satisfies the maximum condition.

In view of the pre-A* poset $A \times A$, with 9 elements defined as in Figure 2, we have the following theorem.

Theorem 5. *If a Pre-A* poset $(A \times A = \{a_1, a_2, \dots, a_9, \leq\})$ with least element of locally finite length satisfies JDCC, then it has a dimension function.*

Fig. 7: An illustration of Theorem 5.

Proof. Let $(A \times A = \{a_1, a_2, \dots, a_9, \leq\})$ be a poset of locally finite length satisfying JDCC. If $A \times A$ contains an element u such that $\inf\{u, x\}$ exists for all $x \in A$, then a dimension function can be defined on A in the following way: For any element u , define

$$\begin{aligned} d(u) &= d_0, \\ d(x) &= d_0 - r_{1x} + r_{2x}, \\ d(y) &= d_0 - r_{1y} + r_{2y}. \end{aligned}$$

The lengths of maximal chains connecting $\inf\{u, x\}$ with u and x are r_{1x} and r_{2x} , respectively. We have to show that d satisfies the following: $x < y$ if and only if $x \leq y$ and $d(x) + 1 = d(y)$ for all x, y in $A \times A$. Let $x, y \in A \times A$ such that $x < y$.

Therefore, $\inf\{u, x\} \leq \inf\{u, y\}$. There exists a maximal chain between $\inf\{u, x\}$ and u which includes $\inf\{u, y\}$. Then the length of the maximal chain between $\inf\{u, x\}$ and $\inf\{u, y\}$ is $r_{1x} - r_{1y}$, as illustrated in Figure 7. Let us denote the length of the maximal chain between x and y by t . By definition, we have:

$$\begin{aligned} d(y) &= d_0 - r_{1y} + r_{2y}, \quad (11) \\ d(x) &= d_0 - r_{1x} + r_{2x}. \quad (12) \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $d(y) - d(x) = (r_{1x} - r_{1y}) + (r_{2y} - r_{2x})$. (13)

Since our poset satisfies JDCC, the lengths of all maximal chains between $\inf\{u, x\}$ and y are equal, that is,

$$r_{1x} - r_{1y} + r_{2y} = r_{2x} + t. \quad (14)$$

From Equations (13) and (14), we have

$$d(y) - d(x) = t. \quad (15)$$

Therefore, $x < y$ if and only if $x \leq y$ and there is no z such that $x \leq z \leq y$. This is equivalent to saying that $x \leq y$ and the lengths of maximal chains connecting x and y is 1. That is, $x \leq y$ and $t = 1$ and hence, $x \leq y$ and by Equation (15), we have that $d(y) = d(x) + 1$. Thus, $x < y$ if and only if $x \leq y$ and $d(x) + 1 = d(y)$ for all $x, y \in A$. This completes the proof.

Remark 3 (Graphical aspect of Figure 7). *The graph has a chromatic number of 2 and is bipartite. Furthermore, the graph in Figure 7 is a subgraph of the bipartite graph $G = A \times A$ in Figure 3. Additionally, the graph in Figure 7 is a planar graph with 2 regions.*

4 TECHNICAL ASPECT

The significance of the crucial element 2 in a Pre-A* algebra is to extend the Boolean two valued logic to three valued logic. That is, if the Boolean elements 0 and 1 stand for false and true statements respectively, then 2 stands for divergence as neither true nor false. The best example of this is a traffic signal system the two basic signals (green light and red light) that can be further extended to another signal (different from green light and red light) depending on a particular situation. The similar logic can be observed in washing machines (Fuzzy logic control systems). The present work is an algebraic study of this logic.

5 APPLICATIONS

Our study on pre-A* posets directly links to graph theory. Given the applications of bipartite graphs in areas such as cancer detection, advertising, e-commerce rankings, prediction of preferences (such as food and movies), and matching problems (such as the stable marriage problem), this work has a lot of potential real-life applications. In fact, we have developed a new way to study graphs using pre-A* poset structures. The use of bipartite graphs to represent binary relations between disjoint sets invites applications of pre-A* posets to medicine and biology, such as bipartite life cycles and bipartite patella for a split kneecap.

6 CONCLUSIONS

We have proven that if a pre-A* poset A has least element of locally finite length and satisfies the Jordan Dedekind chain conditions, then A has a dimension function. We have also established the relationship between pre-A* algebras and graph theory, by giving an analysis of Hasse diagrams. The graph in Figure 7 is subgraph of the one in Figure 2 and both have chromatic number of 2, making them bipartite graphs. The graph in Figure 3 is a planar graph with 5 regions whereas its subgraph in Figure 7 is planar graph with 2 regions.

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